

Counselling Strategies for Reducing Examination Malpractice Among Secondary School Students in Ogidi Education Zone of Anambra State

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Abstract

The study examined counselling strategies for reducing examination and malpractice in Ogidi education zone. The study adopted a descriptive research design and was guided with three research questions. A total of 120 guidance counsellors were used for the study. The whole population served as sample size. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled "Causes, Consequences and Strategies for Reducing Examination Malpractice Questionnaire (C.C.S.R.E.M.Q) developed by the researchers. The data were analyzed using arithmetic mean. The findings showed that examination malpractice among others are caused by insufficient knowledge, lack of confidence, poor study habit, lack of personal time table, poor teaching strategies and its consequences among others includes cancellation of results, Discouragement of honest students from hard work, low productivity, certificate racketeering, loss of credibility and the counselling strategies among others are inculcation of study habit, effective teaching strategies, use of personal time table and guidance on choice of subjects based on aptitudes, interest and abilities to both parents and their children. Based on the findings recommendations were made among, which are guiding and counselling students, parents, teachers and society on causes and consequences of examination malpractices using counselling strategies to reduce examination malpractice.

Key words: Counselling, Strategies, Examination malpractice, guidance and counselling strategies.

Introduction

Education is an indispensable tool for actualizing national development, this could be achieved through equipping the individuals with meaningful knowledge, skills, ideas and technology that could enhance the standard of living of the society concerned (Akaranga & Ongong 2013). The educational institutions are in charge of this noble work. In Nigeria, the educational system operates from primary to secondary school and from secondary to tertiary levels and finally world of work. As the individuals progressed from one level to another, there is need to access and evaluate how far the individuals have acquired this knowledge, skills and ideas for the good of the individuals and the society. But unfortunately this assessments and evaluation is bedeviled with a challenging issue known as examination malpractice

being perpetuated by the candidates, teachers, principles, parents, communities, examination officials and supervisors of the examination bodies (Asuru, 2013).

Examination malpractice has been defined by various researchers. According to Atigbo cited by Egbo (2015), examination malpractice is an unlawful behaviours or activities engaged by students before, during and after examination in a bid to have personal advantage over their colleagues or mates who sat for the same examination. Nwokolo and Oguzie (2021) defined examination malpractice is defined as any act or behaviour by any person or group of persons before, during or after an examination targeted to influence positively the outcome of such examination. Afunugo and Umezulike (2017) see examination malpractice as in appropriate conducts by students during examination. Moreso, examination malpractice is defined as any kind of irrational behaviour exhibited by any person or group of persons before, during or after an examination which contravenes the rules and regulations governing the conducts of such examination (Oguzie, Oguzie, Nnadi, Mokwelu & Obi, 2019). In other words, examination malpractice is any act of omission or commission that undermines the ethics of examination by an individual or groups to earn a candidate an undue grade.

There are various forms of examination malpractices such as giraffe, impersonation, use of ICT, special centres, bringing in foreign and extraneous materials into examination hall, sale of examination papers, disorderliness in examination halls, forgery of results (Uzoigwe 2014; Nnam & Inah, 2015). Oguzie and Nwokolo (2021) observed that examination malpractice may come up in other forms such as bringing of un-authorized materials into the examination hall, collusion, swapping of answer booklets, examination score trading or assault on examination administrators.

Many causes have been suspected as factors responsible for examination malpractice ranging from inadequate preparation for examination, lack of confidence as a result of inadequate preparation, fear or being labeled as a failure, poor teaching, parents support, craze for certificate, poor learning by students. (Akaranga & Ongong 2013; George Ukpong, 2013). According to Oguzie and Nwokolo (2021), overdependence on certificates as the major yardstick to measure students' knowledge and competence may lead to overzealousness on the part of students and their parents to acquire certificates through corrupt means, thereby making them more predisposed to examination malpractice.

However, the consequences of examination malpractice has been suspected to be felt in every aspect of human endeavours such as producing corrupt leaders who has been subjecting the nation into financial quagmire, rogues in the society, quack nurses and doctors, unqualified engineers etc to mention but a few. Nwokolo and Oguzie (2021) stressed that the prevalent rate of bank failures, building collapse, economic sabotage, vandalism, kidnapping, drug trafficking, fake drug manufacturing, among others, may be practical effects of moral decadence emanating from examination malpractice. Examination malpractice has affected the individuals and the society ranging from cancellation of results, discouragement of hard work, low productivity, certificate racketeering, loss of credibility by the nation and difficulty realizing the nations potentials (Onyeibe, Uma & Ibina, 2015).

Examination malpractice has been a serious problem challenging Nigeria educational system in different levels as it increases in intensity as students progresses the education ladder. Reacting to this problem, Oguzie, Oguzie, Nnadi, Mokwelu and Obi (2019) bewailed that examination malpractice is a insidious problem in education and the extent to which secondary school students engage in the crime has become worrisome. Different methods has been applied to checkmate this ugly behaviour such as use of camera, computer based test examination, external invigilators, checking the passport, spacing sitting arrangement, use of continuous assessment (Asore 2014, Akanni & Odofin, 2015). Yet examination malpractice continues to escalate in different dimensions to the extent that students perceive examination

malpractice as a normal way of attaining academic achievement. The need arose to find a lasting solution to examination malpractice. In Ogidi education zone, the researchers observed that most students are seen making savings on how they will maneuver external examinations with connivance of some teachers, parents, examination officials and machineries who created a web site to leak live papers. Most of these students are anxious as they cannot calm down to learn and acquire sufficient knowledge that could enable these students face examination without fear. The teachers are not left out. They try to lobby principals to include their names for external exams as they want to make money through their indulgence in examination malpractice such as bidding the price of subject papers according to order of importance. This calls for the need of guidance counsellors who are trained to change undesirable behaviours to desirable behaviours through the use of counselling services derived from counselling theories and techniques using individual, group counselling and group guidance means to reduce examination malpractice.

Guidance and counselling is one of the educational support services that was introduced to enhance all round development of the child educationally, vocational and psychologically. Research has suggested that many students engage in examination malpractices due to insufficient knowledge and anxiety (Alutu, 2006). This could be traced to inadequate preparation caused by poor teaching and learning, low self efficacy, fear of failing exams and high expectation of the society. These students need educational, vocational and personal social counselling services to enhance their learning process and boost their self efficacy using counselling strategies. Counselling strategies are ways counsellors use in modifying undesirable behaviours to desirable behaviours. The counselling strategies in enhancing learning process include inculcation of study habit to the learners, partnering with teachers to use effective teaching strategies to enhance students acquisition of knowledge, skills ideas, aiding students to prepare their personal time tables, guide students choice of subjects based on interest, abilities and aptitudes, form examination malpractices free club, guide parents and their children on choice of career and institutions based on interest, abilities and aptitudes; value reorientation for students and encourage students to imbibe hard work. All these strategies may enable students acquire sufficient knowledge, become confident to take exams with easiness and shun examination malpractice.

Unfortunately many schools in Ogidi Education Zone do not have counsellors, where they have they are loaded with other school engagement that interfere with provision of needed counselling services that could have helped to reduce examination malpractices. Hence cases of examination malpractice abound in this study area with its consequences such as cancellation of result, discouragement of honest students from hardwork, low productivity, certificate racketeering, loss credibility, difficulty realizing potentials, dismissal, moral decadence, expertise in bribery and corruption and low academic achievement. From this situation therefore, stem the problem of this study which is to determine the causes, consequences and counselling strategies to reduce examination malpractice in Ogidi Education Zone of Anambra state.

Statement of problem

Examination malpractice has been a major issue challenging the education sector. It has taken a tremendous dimension involving not only the students, but includes teachers, administrators, parents, communities, examination officials. Its causes stem from the candidates, and the society while the consequences have been felt by the individuals and the society as well. Efforts have been generated towards its eradication. Yet examination malpractices continue to increase in intensity and dimensions. The persistence of examination malpractices is likely to cause huge loss to the country in terms of national development. The need arose to proffer a lasting solution to this ugly menace. Counselling as a helping profession has the potential to change undesirable behaviours to desirable behaviours through its counselling strategies in terms of proactive or preventive measures. Unfortunately Ogidi education zone lack adequate number of counsellors to guide and counsel students who have the tendency to engage in

examination malpractice. Hence, cases of examination malpractice abound in this area with its attendance consequences. The need arose to come out with counselling strategies to reduce examination malpractice.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study is to investigate the counselling strategies for reducing examination malpractice. Specifically the study determined:

1. Causes of examination malpractice.
2. Consequences of examination malpractice
3. Counselling strategies in reducing examination malpractice.

Research Questions

1. What are the causes of examination malpractice?
2. What are the consequences of examination malpractice?
3. What are the counselling strategies in reducing examination malpractice?

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey design in which a group of people/ item is studied by collecting and analyzing data from item considered to be representative of the entire group. The population of the study is one hundred and twenty counsellors from public schools in Anambra state (P.P.S.S.C, Awka 2020). Since the population is few there is no need for sampling. All the counselors in the state public schools were used in carrying out the research. The instrument used for data collection is a structured questionnaire on the “Causes, Consequences and Strategies for Reducing Examination Malpractice Questionnaire (C.C.S.R.E.M.Q). The questionnaire is to extract and elicit information from the respondents (counselors). A four point scale format was used namely Strongly agree (SA), Agree(A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD).

On the spot administration was embarked upon whereby the researchers visited the counsellors during their monthly meeting and administered the questionnaires which was collected and used for data analysis. The data collected in this study were analyzed using mean, and the critical point was calculated as follows. The mid mean value is 2.50, the decision rule therefore is that any of the response item for which the mean score is 2.50 and above was taken to mean that the respondents agreed while any response item for which the mean is below 2.5 was taken as disagreed.

Results

Table 1: Counsellors’ responses on causes of examination malpractice

S/N	ITEMS	MEAN	DECISION
1.	Insufficient knowledge.	3.8	Agreed
2.	Inadequate preparation.	3.5	Agreed
3.	Lack of confidence.	3.8	Agreed
4.	Fear of failure.	3.5	Agreed
5.	Poor teaching strategies.	3.5	Agreed
6.	Poor study habit	3.2	Agreed
7.	Peer influence	3.0	Agreed
8.	Parents support	2.9	Agreed
9.	Cultism	3.0	Agreed
10.	Craze for certificate	2.8	Agreed

A look at the above table shows that the respondents, on the average, responded affirmatively to all the items regarding the causes of examination malpractices. This was deduced from the fact that the mean scores of all items were higher than the decision mean of 2.50.

Table 2: Counsellors' responses on the consequences of examination mal practices

S/N	ITEMS	MEAN	DECISION
1.	Cancellation of results.	3.2	Agreed
2.	Discouragement of honest students from hard work.	3.2	Agreed
3.	Low productivity.	3.0	Agreed
4.	Certificate racketeering.	3.0	Agreed
5.	Loss of credibility.	3.0	Agreed
6.	Difficulty realizing potentials.	2.9	Agreed
7.	Dismissal	2.8	Agreed
8.	Moral decadence.	2.5	Agreed
9.	High academic achievement.	2.3	Disagreed
10.	Experts in bribery and corruption.	2.5	Agreed

From the above table, apart from item 9 which has a mean score of 2.30, all the other items have their mean scores higher than the decision mean of 2.50. This implies that items 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8 and 10 were accepted as consequences of examination malpractice among counsellors in Ogidi zone based on counsellors perception. On the other hand, item 9 has a mean score of 2.30 which is lower than the decision mean (2.50). It was therefore rejected as a cause of examination malpractice.

Table 3: Counsellors responses on counselling strategies to reduce examination malpractice

S/N	ITEMS	MEAN	DECISION
1.	Inculcation of study habit	3.4	Agreed
2.	Effective teaching strategies.	3.2	Agreed
3.	Use of personal timetable.	3.0	Agreed
4.	Guide students' choice of subjects.	3.3	Agreed
5.	Guide parents' choice of their wards career and institutions.	2.8	Agreed
6.	Value reorientation.	3.0	Agreed
7.	Desensitization of examination fear	3.3	Agreed
8.	Counselling students on use of cognitive learning strategies such as note taking, summarization, etc	3.3	Agreed
9.	Use of one short examination.	2.3	Disagree
10.	Form examination ethics club.	2.5	Agreed
11.	Expulsion	2.3	Disagree
12.	Cognitive behaviour therapy	2.5	Agreed

The above table 3 reveals that items 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,10 and 12 had higher mean than decision mean of 2.50 and therefore were seen as ways of reducing examination malpractice among students. However, items 9 and 11 have a mean score of 2.30 respectively which is lower than the decision mean. Hence, both were rejected as strategies for reducing examination malpractice.

Discussion

The findings of the study in table 1 revealed that examination malpractice in the area of study are caused by the following factors; insufficient knowledge, Inadequate preparation, poor teaching strategies,

poor study habits, peer influence, parents support, cultism and craze for certificate. These causes concur with the findings of other researchers (George & Ukpong, 2013), Akaranga and Ongong (2013), Peters and Okon (2013), Nnam and Inah (2015), Oguzie and Nwokolo (2021) who reported that examination malpractice stem from lack of adequate preparation for examination that directly lead to insufficient knowledge. The insufficient knowledge may be as a result of poor teaching strategies perpetuated by teachers who want recognition for the job not done and then ally with these students to engage in examination malpractice. Such students fear failure and lost confidence to face examination (Obi & Oguzie, 2019). Hence, they indulge in examination malpractice to defuse their fear. These students lack study habit and personal timetable that could have enhance their study. Hence they prefer hanging out with their peers who may not be studios but engage in antisocial activities like cultism that occupies their time rather than studying as they have no interest in their studies. Such students prefer to acquire certificate without its corresponding knowledge and therefore lack job efficiency that leads to low productivity.

The findings from research question two revealed the consequences of examination malpractice on the candidates and the people in Ogidi education Zone. It ranges from cancellation of result, certificate rack steering, loss of credibility, difficulty realizing potentials, dismissal, moral decadence, high academic achievement, and expert in bribery and corruption. This is consistent with the findings of Uzoigwe (2014) who posited that external examination bodies like WAEC and NECO are known for cancellation of result and closure of centers found with examination malpractice. This might not augur well for some students who may not engage themselves with examination malpractices, and can discourage honest students from hard work and thereby reduce their high morale for their studies. This agreed with the findings of another researcher Uzoigwe (2014) who found that most students cannot defend their certificates. The study also agree with the findings of previous researchers who reported that examination malpractice results to certificate racketeering as there is this mad rush to certificate acquisition devoid of knowledge acquisition that lead to loss of credibility (Oguzie, Oguzie, Nnadi, Mokwelu & Obi, 2019; Onyeibe, Uma & Ibina, 2015). Some of these candidates regard certificate as a means of acquiring wealth without corresponding knowledge and skills that could be offered to acquire wealth. Hence, their certificate may not guarantee job efficiency. This has affected the productivity level as some of these candidates cannot perform and deliver based on the quality of certificate they possess even within and outside the country hence they destroy the national integrity.

Finally the study revealed that the counselling strategies for reducing examination malpractice include inculcation of study habits, effective teaching strategies, use of personal time table, guiding students choice of subject based on interest, abilities and aptitudes, guide parents choice of career and institutions for their children, value re-orientation, desensitization of examination fear, counselling students on use of cognitive learning strategies and formation of examination ethics clubs . From the findings, it was observed that inculcation of study habit, counselling teachers on the use of effective teachings strategies, desensitizing students from examination fear, guiding students on choice of subjects based on interest, aptitude and abilities were commonly employed in reducing examination malpractice. This concur with the findings other researchers Sobari and Eremie (2018) who found that students who study very well, choose subjects according to their abilities and aptitudes, taught by effective and embrace examination ethics and do not engage in examination malpractice. However, expulsion and use of one short examination were rarely used to reduce examination malpractice. This agree with the findings of other researchers (Udim, Abubakar & Essien, 2018; Unachukwu & Ezimorah Nwanneka, 2018) who found that expulsion of students who engage in examination mal practice will serve as deterrents to other students. An effective counsellor would have earlier dictate such students and apply counselling techniques such as cognitive behaviour therapy via group and individual counselling to ameliorate the situation rather than expulsion.

Implication for counselling

The danger of examination malpractice should be x-rayed to the students, their parents and society generally who offer support to their children and their cohorts in carrying out this ugly acts through individual, group counselling, group guidance, parent teachers meeting and seminar. The students engage in examination malpractice as a result of insufficient knowledge and lack of confidence while teachers ally with students to perpetuate this act because of inadequate delivery of their job. The society craves for certificate acquisition without corresponding knowledge and skills.

The society is filled with mediocre and half baked personnel who cannot guarantee job efficiency hence bribery and corruption is the order of the day. For the fact that examination malpractice is bedeviled with dangerous effects to individuals and society, the option left is to fight against examination malpractice with available counselling strategies. Counselling strategies should be applied earlier from primary school to stop students and their cohorts from engaging in examination malpractice.

Conclusion

This work explored the causes, consequences and counselling strategies for reducing examination malpractice among students in Ogidi education zone of Anambra state. The following conclusions were made:

1. Students, teachers, parents and the society are involved in examination malpractice.
2. Both students and the society bear the effects of examination malpractice.
3. Counselling strategies are possible strategies to curb examination mal practice.

Recommendation

Consequent to the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Guidance counselors should disseminate information regarding the dangers of examination malpractice within and outside the school setting through orientation, seminars and youth organizations programmes.
2. Counsellors should synergies with teachers to teach students with effective teaching strategies that can guarantee effective learning with coverage of scheme of work.
3. Counsellors should give a talk to the parents on the issue of examination mal practice concerning the consequences of examination malpractice to the candidates and society.
4. Counsellors should be posted to schools to apply preventive strategies that could reduce the tendency to engage in examination malpractice.
5. Counsellors should inculcate good study habit, encourage students to embark on group study and to desensitize students from examination malpractice.
6. The government should deemphasize certificate acquisition but emphasize practical knowledge and skill acquisition.
7. Finally the researchers advocate that government should promulgate a decree or policy to punish those who connive with students in carrying out this ugly act.

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